

THE INFLUENCE OF SPECIMEN SIZE ON THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS
OF SQUEEZE CAST METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Optimum manufacturing process range for the squeeze casting of small size metal matrix composite(MMC)s, obtained by measuring the bonding strength at the interface and the tensile strength, is applied extensively for the squeeze casting of actual large size MMCs. Influential manufacturing parameters such as the applied pressure, preheating of the mold , and the time before applying the pressure are separately investigated referring to the basic theory and experimental observations. The effects of different constituent materials on the microstructures and the mechanical properties are also investigated. The results propose a systematic way to bridge the gap between the optimum manufacturing process of the squeeze casting of the small size and the actual large size MMCs.

KEY WORDS: Squeeze Casting; Matrix, Aluminum; Optimization; Manufacturing; Size Effect

1. INTRODUCTION

Production of sound metal matrix composite(MMC)s has been tried by various processing methods[1,2] even though reinforcing ceramic fibers are reluctant to adhere to the matrix metals[3]. Some results have shown very successful so as to apply for actual engineering structures[4,5]. However, even successful methods so far do not prove their reproducibility in subsequent large scale production. The aim of this paper is therefore to investigate whether an optimum manufacturing process of squeeze casting obtained for small size MMCs could be extended to actual production size without any significant change. The optimum manufacturing process of squeeze cast small size MMCs was previously obtained

by measuring the bonding strength at the interface and the tensile strength of continuous SiC/Al composites[6]. Referring to this condition, the effects of process parameters - applied pressure, the temperature of preheating the mold, and delay time before applying the pressure - on the large size MMCs are investigated. For the effect of the applied pressure, increasing pressure drop during the matrix impregnation is observed on the basis of three dimensional Blake-Kozeny equations[7]. Different pressure drop due to the design of the mold is also investigated for the same volume of MMC specimen. The uniform distribution of the mold is considered with respect to the mold design and the heating method. The delay time is also considered to correlate between the temperature history of the molten matrix, phase diagram of the matrix, and the mold temperature. The effects of different constituent materials - different diameters and chemical compositions of available fibers such as Tyranno Si-Ti-C fiber, Nicalon SiC fiber, and Cyanamid Ni coated carbon fiber, and different Al alloy matrices such as 2024, 6061, and 7075 Al - on the microstructures and the mechanical properties of fabricated MMCs are systematically investigated. For the microstructural observation, optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy analysis as well as energy dispersive X-ray analysis are performed for MMCs prepared by different manufacturing process conditions. In the observation of mechanical properties, tensile strengths of Si-Ti-C/Al composites are measured to correlate with the variation of microstructure of the matrix. For Nicalon SiC/Al composites, flexural strengths are measured by three point bending test in order to optimize the processing conditions. Combining the results of flexural strengths with the microstructural observation, it can be suggested what are significant factors for the optimum processing range of large size MMCs.

2. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

2.1 Fabrication of MMCs Two kinds of continuous SiC fibers which have different diameters and chemical compositions and Ni coated carbon fiber are selected for reinforcements. Their properties are briefly summarized in Table 1. The matrices used are 2024, 6061, and 7075 Al alloys to know the effect of additives on the interfacial morphology.

Fiber	Composition	Crystalline Species	Diameter (mm)	Tensile Strength (GPa)
Nicalon SiC	54.3 Si, 30.0 C, 11.8 O	b - SiC	15	2.5
Tyranno Si-Ti-C	44.2 Si, 24.5 C, 12.3 O 11.0 Ti	b-SiC + TiC	8	1.99
Cyanamid Ni coated carbon	PAN	Ni on Carbon	7.6	4.36

Table 1 Properties of reinforcement fibers

The preform of continuous fibers is prepared with pins and a holder as shown in Figure 1. Fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation both are adjusted by changing the distance between grooves in a pin and the winding angle. Fibers between the pins are pulled as tight as possible to keep the original fiber placement during the matrix impregnation. The molds used in this study are two kinds. One is two piece separate mold (Figure 2(a)) which is convenient to remove the MMC specimen after the process. The other is one piece assembled mold (Figure 2(b)) which is good for no pressure loss during applying the pressure. The design of these molds is in principle different from that of the small size MMC mold which has low depth and wide open area perpendicular to the direction of the applied pressure. However, this newly designed mold has high depth and narrow open area to produce large size MMCs.

Figure 1. Preform preparation

Figure 2. (a) Two-piece separate mold (b) One piece assembled mold

2.2 Processing Range Optimum manufacturing process range of small size MMCs which have the dimension of L100mm x W8mm x H10 mm is obtained by measuring the bonding strength at the fiber/matrix interface and the tensile strengths of MMC specimens. The optimum range is 40 ~ 75 MPa for the applied pressure, 300 ~ 500 °C for preheating the preform and the punch, 100 °C higher than the matrix melting temperature for overheating the matrix, and less than 10 seconds for the delay time before applying the pressure. In this large size MMC fabrication, there are few different manufacturing circumstances from the above small size MMC fabrication, which are (1) no vacuum assisted during the heating of the mold and the matrix and no heating of the punch for making the process simple (2) narrow open area and high depth mold to the applied pressure direction (3) large volume of molten matrix to pour into the preform for large size. Previously, vacuum assistance in squeeze casting was adapted to remove the impurity on the fiber surface and to reduce the matrix oxidation during the process. In order to compensate of these effects in this study, it may be necessary to increase the applied pressure even though it is difficult to determine its absolute effect. Increased depth of the mold also causes to increase the frictional resistance along the mold wall as well as the pressure drop along the longer fiber bundles expressed by Blake-Kozeny equations[7]. In general, the range of temperatures for preheating the mold and overheating the matrix is considered with respect to the wetting angle between the fiber and the matrix[9]. Thus, it is not affected by the specimen size directly. The delay time before applying the pressure has to be considered on the basis of the mushy zone state of the molten matrix. As the volume of the molten matrix becomes larger, the delay time should be reduced compared with the time for small size. This delay time is fixed less than 3 seconds here referring to the cooling rate and the phase diagram of the matrix materials. Regarding these considerations, the processing range for large size MMCs is tried to follow the conditions as summarized and denoted as Table 2. The overheating temperature of the matrix is fixed 800 °C for all conditions.

Applied pressure / Preheating temp.	50 MPa	75 MPa	100 MPa
300 °C	#1	#4	#7
400 °C	#2	#5	#8
500 °C	#3	#6	#9

Table 2. Processing ranges for large size MMCs

3. RESULTS

3.1 Microstructural Observation The effect of the applied pressure on different diameters

of the fibers is investigated. Figure 3 shows the microstructures of Si-Ti-C/2024 Al MMCs fabricated by the processing conditions of #2 and #8 in Table 2. With the applied pressure 100 MPa, the matrix is not impregnated enough into the bundles of relatively small diameters of Si-Ti-C fibers. Figure 4 shows the microstructures of Nicalon SiC/2024 Al MMCs fabricated by the processing conditions of #2 and #5 in Table 2. With the applied pressure 75 MPa, the surfaces of the fibers are more or less damaged. Thus, the appropriate applied pressure for Nicalon SiC/2024Al is thought to be between 50 MPa and 75 MPa. Figure 5 (a) shows the microstructures of Ni coated carbon fiber/2024 Al fabricated by the processing condition of #8. As the diameter of this fiber is as small as Si-Ti-C fiber, it is also found insufficient impregnation of the matrix into the fiber bundles. Besides this insufficient matrix impregnation, thin Ni coating layer on the carbon fiber is resolved into the matrix as solid state as shown in Figure 5 (b). It is confirmed by mapping the same area of Figure 5 (b) and the line profiling of energy dispersive X-ray analysis along the interfaces as shown in Figure 6 (a) and (b).

Figure 3. Microstructures of Si-Ti-C/2024 Al (a) #2 processing condition (applied pressure 50 MPa) (b) #8 processing condition (applied pressure 100 MPa)

Figure 4. Microstructures of Nicalon SiC/2024 Al (a) #2 processing condition (applied pressure 50 MPa) (b) #5 processing condition (applied pressure 75 MPa)

Figure 5. Microstructures of Ni coated Carbon/2024 Al (a) transverse section
(b) longitudinal section

Figure 6. (a) Mapping of Ni coated carbon/2024 Al (b) energy dispersive X-ray analysis

3.2 Mechanical Properties Tensile strengths of Si-Ti-C/2024 Al MMCs fabricated by the processing conditions of #1 to #9 in Table 2 are measured according to ASTM D3552[10]. Figure 7 shows their results compared with those of small size Nicalon SiC/Al MMCs. Tensile strengths of Si-Ti-C/2024 Al shown in Figure 7 are fabricated by #7 condition which produces the highest tensile strength in 9 limited conditions. Flexural strengths of Nicalon SiC/Al MMCs are measured to determine the optimum condition for large size MMC in the conditions of Table 2. The test procedure is referred to ASTM D790. Figure 8 shows the variation of flexural strengths of SiC/2024 Al MMCs with respect to the mold temperature and the applied pressure. The higher the applied pressure and the lower the mold temperature gives higher flexural strengths of SiC/2024 Al MMCs. Figure 9 shows the variation of flexural strengths of SiC/Al MMCs with respect to the mold temperature and the

matrix. It shows the same tendency as Figure 8 for the effect of the mold temperature on the flexural strength. However, it tells that mechanical behaviors of composites are not corresponding to those of the matrix itself. It means that the strength of 2024 Al itself is only 75 % of 7075 Al itself. However, the strength of SiC/2024 Al is higher than 120% of SiC/7075 Al.

Figure 7. Comparison of tensile strength between Nicalon SiC/Al and Tyranno Si-Ti-C/Al

Figure 8. Flexural strengths of Nicalon SiC/2024 Al with respect to the applied pressure

Figure 9. Flexural strengths of Nicalon SiC/Al with respect to Al matrices

4. DISCUSSIONS

From Figure 3 and Figure 4, it is found that the applied pressure is more required for smaller diameter of the fiber to fill the matrix into the fiber bundles without voids. This phenomena could be predicted by the theoretical consideration with Blake-Kozeny equations[7]; the pressure drop along the fibers is higher in smaller diameter of the fibers which have larger surfaces. However, this result does not agree with that of Fukunaga[11] who claims that there are no visible change of microstructure in SiCp/Al-4%Cu when the applied pressure is over 50 MPa. This disagreement could be explained in different morphologies and diameters of the fibers and the pressure loss in this kind of mold design. For the matter of temperature effect,

the high depth mold causes serious temperature non-uniformity in upper and lower part of the mold, which consequently brings non-uniform microstructures of fabricated MMCs. Thus, it is meaningless to consider the effect of the temperature on the properties of MMCs without having uniform temperature distribution in the mold. From Figure 5, it is found that even though the processing temperature is lower than the melting temperature of Ni, coating layer of Ni on the carbon fiber seems to be resolved into the matrix as solid state. Thus, the Ni coating on the carbon fiber might be unstable under the applied pressure and the temperature of #8 processing condition. This suggest that it may be to reduce the applied pressure even though the Ni coated carbon fiber needs high applied pressure to impregnate the matrix into small diameters of fiber bundle or to decrease the preheating temperature of the fibers.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The size effects on the manufacturing process in squeeze cast MMCs are investigated to find the basic ground for reliable and reproducible processing conditions. The intermediate conclusions could be drawn as follows;

Under the same processing conditions, the microstructure and the mechanical properties of the MMCs are strongly dependent on the diameter and the chemical composition of the fibers. The required applied pressure is very dependent on the specimen size and which relation is dominated by Blake-Kozeny equations. The size effect on the temperature is relatively less than on the applied pressure because the temperature parameter in the squeeze casting just relates the wettability between the constituent materials. However, the uniform temperature distribution in the mold plays a critical role because which consequently makes uniform properties of MMCs. In order to make it, the mold for squeeze casting should be designed as low depth and wide open area for the same volume of MMCs.

6. REFERENCES

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